

UNDERSTANDING FOOD INSECURITY: CAUSES, IMPACT AND SOLUTIONS

Dr. Sana Saima¹, Riya Bajaj², Sanjana K³, Avika Gupta⁴, Rithish S M⁵, Sanjay Patel⁶

¹Assistant professor CMS JAIN (deemed-to-be) University.

^{2,3,4,5,6}Student CMS JAIN (deemed-to-be) University

Abstract - Food insecurity has been a global issue that has been affecting a large number of people across the globe. This study aims to determine the prevalence of food insecurity that disproportionately affects people and identify the demographics which are most affected, including age, their income levels, and the geographic location. We performed a survey for primary research which included 50 individuals, this research helped us analyze the social, economic, and environmental factors that are leading to food insecurity. Moreover, the effectiveness in reducing food insecurity was critically evaluated through current policies and reforms made for this issue. The findings showcase significant correlations between the affordability of individuals, government schemes in their community as well as the basic awareness about the existence of food insecurity in today's society. This study suggests policies and best practices to improve food access and security.

Key Words: Food insecurity, economic factors, social impact, government policies

INTRODUCTION

Food insecurity can be defined as a lack of access to nutritious and sufficient food consistently for a healthy life. It's when people are unaware of when they will eat or when their next meal will be, a problem that is affecting millions of people worldwide due to various reasons like economic instability, social inequalities, and environmental changes. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and World Health Organization (WHO) aim to solve the issue that is related to the sustainable development goal no.2 world hunger. FAO strives to eradicate hunger, food insecurity, and all forms of malnutrition. Supporting the livelihoods of small-scale food producers, improving the resilience of food production systems, and encouraging the sustainable use of natural resources are all key to fulfilling this mandate and achieving [Sustainable Development Goal 2](#) (SDG2), a world without hunger, food insecurity, and malnutrition.

Research Problem

Despite various schemes and government reforms across the world through various organizations, food insecurity continues to be a problem, especially among low-income individuals and certain demographic groups. Food insecurity can be experienced at different levels of severity according to the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) and Prevalence of Undernourishment (PoU) - adequate access to food but may be uncertain about future access (food security or mild food

insecurity), compromising on food quality and verity and reducing food quantity and skipping meals (moderate food insecurity), no food access for a day or more (severe food insecurity). These help us analyze food insecurity across the globe.

Objective of the study

1. Examine the prevalence and demographics of food insecurity
2. Analyze causes and the contributing factors
3. Identify gaps in research and propose directions for future studies.

Literature Review

Food insecurity is a major issue for so many people around the world and in India it's growing rapidly even every part of the country is facing and in India urban poor households. Every time urban food insecurity is underestimated in the global discussion and economic inequality can be the reason for food insecurity in cities Mumbai is considered one of the developed and largest cities still a part of the population is living in slums and going through food insecurity. (Chatterjee et al, 2012)

Economic factors: poverty is one of the greatest concerns of food insecurity. Many households in Mumbai are in low-income neighborhoods and employment in the informal sector is suffering from low income without any social security benefits. Social inequalities: depending upon gender caste social status people are treated it shows how women and different cast people discriminated against in urban India are more likely to suffer from food insecurity. Research suggests how economic factors and social inequality play a role and contribute to food insecurity. It also gives insight for policymakers working to deal with food insecurity in developed cities.

Food insecurity in India remains a key concern with so many people across the country unable to obtain the right amount of nutrient. It defines food insecurity as a problem involving different factors like attainability, financial accessibility, and use food insecurity in India is mainly associated with social political economic factors. The main relation in this article is the connection between food insecurity and economic poverty. A significant part of India is deprived which limits their access to food social factors also affect such as caste gender age discrimination women in particular are more vulnerable to suffer from malnutrition. This highlights the need to have multidimensional approaches to handle food insecurity (Sujoy Chakravarty, Sejal A Dand, 2005)

This study talks about how food insecurity affects physical as well as mental health during pregnancy it can worsen mental health that includes depression and anxiety it is found that pregnant women who suffer from food insecurity were more likely to develop depression compared to those who have enough food nutrition result shows that food insecurity is related to increased chance of depression during pregnancy but the prove quality was low due to differences in studies it is suggested to address food insecurity and mental health during pregnancy is really important and public policies ensuring better access to food could improve mental health situation for pregnant women.(Camila Biete, 2024)

In this it focuses on the issue of food insecurity in older populations and low middle income countries this is a serious concern now it is affecting older person this is focused on the personal factors related to food insecurity like income health status and education there were very less studies which can help tracking how good insecurity changes over time for older people mostly studies were quantitative they relied on numbers and statistics this research only showed 15 different low and middle income countries that means many part were not represented .(Carolina Neves Freiria, 2024)

Covid 19 pandemic has severely affected people life across various sectors globally and food insecurity worsens the conditions India being one of the most affected countries the pandemic disturbed both the supply and demand for the food lockdown restrictions closures have led to increase in prices for the food and lack of access large segment of people struggled for basic food needs women and children specifically have to suffer more as they require special dietary women in low income families are the first to reduce Their food consumption leads to malnutrition (Khushbu Mishra,2020)

This study talks about how during COVID-19 in the USA there was a survey to analyse how the stay at home period caused challenges for people to access food and other basic needs. People were facing food insecurity for the first time on a large scale, due to the major job losses or reduced work hours. Households which had children and women were facing more problems compared to the men due to lack of nutrition. Two- thirds of the households reported eating less. This led to a need to come up with strategies to deal with food accessibility challenges and supporting the vulnerable part of the population during such a crisis.(Meredith T. Niles,2020)

This talks about study conducted on nutrition and the relation between food insecurity and mental health outcomes like stress, depression, anxiety. Using the random effects model and standard inclusion criteria an observation was conducted. Which told us that people experiencing food insecurity were at a 40% higher risk of depression, there was a 34% increase in stress in these individuals, which also led to anxiety. Participants above the age 65 experience depression and anxiety more compared to other individuals due to a lack of proper food nutrition, food insecure households in certain

regions experienced more of the mental health risks. Addressing the improvement of food insecurity can help improve the mental health problems in individuals.(Ali Pourmotabbed,2020)

Women's health and food insecurity have major relations leading to many problems and risks. Obesity among women due to limited access to nutritious food may contribute to weight gain, many mental health risks like anxiety and depression in women are seen. There is also an adoption of poor coping mechanisms. There are negative outcomes to pregnant women due to lack of proper nutritious food. There needs to be further research to clarify the major causes and getting proper interventions to address food insecurity among women. (Louise C. Ivers, 2011)

The study provides an analysis of how food insecurity is assessed across india. There are over 200 million malnourished individuals that are under a risk of food insecurity. There are several initiatives provided for these individuals by the government and reportedly 8.7% to 99% food insecurity rates were analyzed, there was a gap in the longitudinal research that could offer deeper insights into trends and factors of the food insecurity. While in the urban setting 51% to 77% of people were facing food insecurity, whereas in rural areas more than 70% people were at the risk. Given the widespread malnutrition and high prevalence of food insecurity in India, critical steps need to be taken to enhance nutrition related public health initiatives. (Fiona H. McKay, 2023)

The study talks about how food insecurity leads to major issues to children's health. Families' selection into proper nutritious food and understanding the impacts of nutrition in kids influences their health and mental development and wellbeing, if proper nutrition is not provided it leads to severe development issues and mental health risk. Children from food-secure households are more likely to be reported in good health and mental well-being, a healthy likelihood of maintaining healthy weight was observed among food-secure children. This analysis tells us the importance of addressing food insecurity as a means to improve children's health outcomes that are affected due to many reasons. (Craig Gundersen, 2009)

Reports of lived experience pointed to the causal nature of economic conditions. Paying for rent and food were the top financial concerns of food-insecure households; however, high and rising food prices were the most frequently cited barriers to adopting healthier diets and adding nutrition to their food. Food-insecure households spent less on food, reporting poor and worsening diet quality and more limited access to meat, fresh vegetables and fresh fruit; this created insecurity which was linked to higher rates of obesity, diabetes, asthma and other chronic conditions related to health. Food-insecure respondents reported more stress, anxiety and depression which all sums up to the non nutritious food in their diet (Adam D,2022)

We present a novel and rigorous approach to determining the impact of climate change, as manifested in heat stress, defined

as the temperature anomaly relative to a historic baseline, on food security. To do this, we had to overcome a number of substantive methodological challenges with regards to both data analysis and data. Starting off with , the relationship between climate and food security evolves and changes over time, and so a time constant regression framework, as is commonly used in the existing literature on climate and socioeconomic outcomes, is insufficient. We therefore use a time-varying regression, which can be tricky to operationalise and computationally intensive. Following which, until recently, standardised data on food insecurity for a sufficient number of countries has been hard to access. It can be observed here that we sourced and merged data from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) for 83 countries. Then, we had to define an appropriate measure of climate change. We chose to focus on temperature, defined as the annual deviation from a long-term rolling mean. Hence, from this approach the controlling for other key factors that have been demonstrated to affect food insecurity, including extreme events, specifically droughts; and “development”, as proxied by sub-national HDI we are able to quantify the extent to which food security has already been negatively affected by climate change (Shroud,2022)

Food insecurity in urban America is closely linked to socioeconomic disparities, with income inequality, unemployment, and racial inequities playing significant roles this created low-income households, particularly in cities, face limited access to affordable, nutritious food due to factors like poverty, housing instability, and food deserts (Coleman-Jensen et al., 2019). These challenges disproportionately affect racial and ethnic minorities, contributing to health disparities (Smith, J., & Johnson, L.,2022)

This report provides statistics on food security in U.S. households throughout 2022 based on the Current Population Survey Food Security Supplement data collected by the U.S. Department of Commerce, Bureau of the Census, in December 2022. An estimated 87.2 % of U.S. households were food secure throughout the entire year in 2022, with access at all times to enough food for an active, healthy life for all household members. The remaining households were food insecure at least some time during the year, including 5.1 % with very low food security (Hales J Jordan,2022)

Ninety-eight relevant studies were included for data charting with 37 unique measurement tools, 115 risk factors, and 93 possible consequences of food insecurity identified. This led to the examination that factors linked to racial discrimination, behaviour, or risk factors that mapped to the food availability dimension of food security. Infrequently studied factors, such as lifetime racial discrimination, socioeconomic status (SES), and income insecurity need further investigation while frequently studied factors such as age, education, race/ethnicity, and gender need to be summarized using a systematic review approach so that risk factor impact can be better assessed (angela D. Liese PhD a 2 4,2022)

Research Methodology:

Data Collection:

The data was collected using Primary and Secondary sources of data collection.

The primary data was collected through a self-made questionnaire.

The secondary data collected is the published information from reports, research papers, articles, and the internet.

Sampling Technique:

Simple Random Sampling was used to collect the data. This method is the most straightforward of all the probability sampling methods, since it only involves a single random selection and requires little advanced knowledge about the population.

In the context of the study conducted on food insecurity data analysis involves examining the collected information from the questionnaire responded by 50 respondents.

Data analysis

The findings reveal a regional disparity in awareness with urban respondents being more familiar with food insecurity than the semi-urban areas. It can be pointed out that limited access to information may contribute to this gap. The main drivers of food insecurity are the economic factors where many people believe that “poverty”, “the rising cost of food” and “inflation” has a further impact on affordability and being unaware of multiple food assistance programs. The key barriers to nutritious food and poor quality and high costs of food with limited options.

As a result, this has led to an increase in health issues due to inadequate nutrition and many regularly notice low-quality food in the markets. However, the solutions observed in this study favor meal preparation skills, support learning for low-cost nutritious food, and give more priority to creative cooking. These findings stress the need for policy reform and community-driven interventions to enhance food quality.

Interpretation:

Age group

Interpretation- The majority of respondents (77.4%) belong to the 18-28 age group, indicating that young adults form the largest segment of the audience. The 29-39 and 40-50 age group each account for 11.3%, suggesting a balanced but significantly smaller representation from older demographics.

Are you familiar with the term 'food insecurity'?

Interpretation- The majority (64.2%) are familiar with the term highlighting strong awareness. However 18.9% are unaware about it and 17% are uncertain, indicating the need to create awareness.

Which area do you belong to?

Interpretation- A significant majority of respondents (75.5%) belong to urban areas indicating strong urban presence. Semi urban sum up to 20.8% signifying moderate participation whereas the rural population is the smallest segment highlighting the limited engagement from rural areas.

What do you believe is the primary cause of food insecurity ?

Interpretation- Rising food costs are perceived as the major cause 45.3%, and also poverty being another reason 26.4%. While the Lack of access to food markets 20.8% respondents felt was the primary cause of food insecurity and climate change/natural disasters 7.5% respondents felt are considered less significant factors, though still relevant.

How has inflation impacted your ability to afford food?

Interpretation- 47.2% of respondents feel moderately impacted with inflation, while 28.3% report slight effects due to the impacts of inflation. 11.3% respondents state significant struggles, whereas 13.2% claim no impact, highlighting varied experiences with inflation.

Are you aware of any government or community programs that provide food assistance in your area?

Interpretation- A majority of respondents (58.5%) are not aware of any government or community programs. Meanwhile, 30.2% are aware of it and 11.3% are uncertain indicating a significant gap in awareness, suggesting the need for better communication on the available programs.

Do you believe food waste is a concern in your community despite food insecurity issues?

Interpretation- A majority of the respondents (60.4%) believe food waste is a concern despite food insecurity issues. However, 20.8% do not see it as a significant issue, while 18.9% are uncertain. This indicates a potential gap in awareness of differing perspectives on the issue.

Have you participated in any food relief programs or received support from NGOs, charities, or welfare schemes?

Interpretation - 56.6% of respondents have not participated in any food relief programs or received support from NGOs, charities, or welfare schemes. whereas, 43.4% of respondents feel they don't see a benefit from such initiatives. This shows that while a considerable

number of people have accessed food relief, more efforts may be needed to reach those in need.

If you've participated in a food assistance program, how effective do you believe it was in meeting your needs?

Interpretation- A majority of the respondents (62.3%) believe that the food assistance programs are somewhat effective. Meanwhile, 22.6% believe they're extremely effective and 15.1% believe they're not at all effective suggesting the need to improvise on the same.

respondents see improving job opportunities as the best solution, long-term economic stability is seen as less immediately impactful compared to direct food support programs.

Do you believe policymakers are doing enough to address food insecurity in your area?

Interpretation- A majority 54.7% of respondents believe that policymakers don't do enough to address food insecurity in their area, showcasing the dissatisfaction with current policies. Whereas 28.3% believe policymakers make sufficient efforts, 17% of respondents are uncertain showing the population is unaware regarding the issue.

Which type of intervention do you think would be most effective in improving food security?

Interpretation- Majority of respondents(47.2%) believe that the educational programs on budgeting and meal planning are the most effective interventions to improve food insecurity. 22.6% believe that subsidized food programs are effective. 20.8%believe that free meal distribution is most effective. However 9.4% of

Are you aware of any government or community programs that provide food assistance in your area?

Interpretation- 58.5% of the respondents were unaware about the government or community food assistance

programs, this showed that there is a gap in outreach or accessibility of information, however 23.3% respondents were aware of such programs. 13.2% were unsure, which tells us there's a need for better communication and engagement.

Interpretation- When asked about the challenges in accessing affordable nutritious food 58.5% of respondents found high prices of healthy food as a challenge, where as 56.6% of the respondents said it was the quality of the food that was poor. 41.5% of respondents struggled with limited options], showing the restricted access to nutritious food. However only 11.3% of respondents reported facing no such challenges , showing that the accessibility to food was not an issue.

Have you faced a reduction in food availability due to environmental changes (e.g.,droughts, floods)?

Have you or anyone in your family faced health issues due to lack of nutritious food ?

Interpretation- When asked about the environmental changes on food availability,39.6% respondents reported less food availability due to environmental factors like droughts and floods, 41.5% respondents did not know or notice any significant impacts. However 18.9% respondents were not sure regarding the climate related food challenges.

Interpretation- 60.4% of respondents reported that they or their families have faced health issues due to lack of nutritious food, showing the direct impact of food on health. 39.6% have not experienced any health concerns related to lack of nutritious food.

What challenges do you face when trying to access affordable and nutritious food?

Have you noticed a rise in counterfeit or low-quality food products in your local markets?

Interpretation- 60.4% of respondents often noticed a rise in counterfeit or low - quality products in local markets while 17% noticed them frequently. However 18.9% of respondents rarely came across such issues and a very small percentage report they have never noticed such things. Showcasing the growing concerns related to food quality and safety .

Which Indian government initiative do you believe has been most effective in addressing food insecurity?

Interpretation-The mid day meal scheme was seen as most effective by 43.4% respondents, the national food security act was seen as effective by 30.2% respondents. On the other hand integrated child development services were seen as effective by 11.3%and the public distribution system had 7.5% respondents finding it effective and a small percentage that is 7.5% believed none of the initiatives were addressing food insecurity.

What type of skills or resources would best help you manage food insecurity?

Interpretation- Meal preparation tips for affordable cooking was the choice of majority of respondents 38.5%, learning about nutritious low-cost meals were 28.3% respondents choice showcasing an interest in balancing nutrition with affordability. 26.4% respondents chose budgeting and financial planning as a resource to manage food insecurity. Whereas 9.4% respondents said that access to community support networks was their source to manage food insecurity showing that few people see external community resources as their primary need.

Which community-based solution do you believe would best improve food security in your area?

Interpretation- 24.5% respondents believed that more affordable grocery stores and community gardens or urban farming would improve food insecurity. 22.6% respondents believed that expanded food assistance programs and cooking and nutrition education programs were the best way to improve food insecurity showing that there's an interest in support and education initiatives.5.7% respondents believed that increased access to local markets showed that respondents prioritized affordability and assistance over expanded markets.

If food prices continue to rise, what would be your top priority?

Interpretation- A majority (54.7%) indicated that Finding ways to cook creatively on a budget would be their top priority, underscoring the importance of meal preparation skills. Reducing non-food expenses to manage better was chosen by 24.5%, suggesting that nearly a quarter of respondents would adjust their overall financial priorities. Prioritizing cheaper, filling foods over nutrition was selected by 13.2%, highlighting a potential shift towards affordability over dietary quality. The least chosen option, Relying more on community support programs at 7.5%, suggests that most respondents prefer self-sufficiency over external assistance.

Which essential nutrients do you struggle to include in your diet regularly?

Interpretation- 45.3% of respondents struggle to include protein in their diet making it most lacking nutrients, while 37.7% respondents find it difficult to consume enough fruits and vegetables showing a gap in

consumption of micronutrients, whereas 17% respondents show no difficulty in maintaining a balanced diet.

How confident are you that food insecurity can be significantly reduced in the next 5 years?

Interpretation- When asked if respondents would see a decline or betterment in the next 5 years in food insecurity 35.8% of respondents are somewhat confident that food insecurity can be reduced in the next five years. 32.1% remain neutral, 17% are not confident showing they are unsure about the improvement, 13.2% are very confident that they will see a change in the next five years, and minimal 2% are unsure about the potential for change.

Findings:

1. Urban Dominance in Awareness – The majority of respondents (75.5%) belong to urban areas, with a higher level of awareness about food insecurity compared to semi-urban (20.8%) and rural areas (3.7%).
2. Economic Factors Drive Food Insecurity – within the rise of food costs (45.3%) and poverty (26.4%) are the primary causes of food insecurity along with inflation affecting food affordability for nearly half (47.2%) of our respondents.
3. Limited Awareness and Participation in Food Assistance Programs – Over 58.5% of respondents are unaware of government or community food programs, and 56.6% have never participated in any food relief initiatives.
4. Barriers to Accessing Nutritious Food – High prices (58.5%), poor food quality (56.6%), and limited availability (41.5%) are the main challenges, with 60.4% of respondents experiencing health issues due to lack of nutritious food.
5. Preferred Solutions Focus on Education and Affordability – Meal preparation techniques (35.8%) and learning how to make nutritious low-cost meals (28.3%) are seen as key skills,

while 54.7% would prioritize creative cooking if food prices continue to rise.

Discussions :

The findings reveal a regional disparity in awareness with urban respondents being more familiar with food insecurity than the semi-urban areas. It can be pointed out that limited access to information may contribute to this gap. The main drivers of food insecurity are the economic factors where many people believe that “poverty”, “the rising cost of food” and “inflation” has a further impact on affordability and being unaware of multiple food assistance programs. The key barriers to nutritious food and poor quality and high costs of food with limited options.

As a result, this has led to an increase in health issues due to inadequate nutrition and many regularly notice low-quality food in the markets. However, the solutions observed in this study favor meal preparation skills, support learning for low-cost nutritious food, and give more priority to creative cooking. These findings stress the need for policy reform and community-driven interventions to enhance food quality.

Limitations of the study

1. **Sample Size and Representation:** The study does not cover the entire population due to a small sample size, focusing on specific groups. Rural and urban populations are underrepresented, and the sample lacks diversity across different regions and socioeconomic backgrounds.
2. **Self-Report Data Bias:** Since responses are based on personal experiences and perceptions, there is a possibility of response bias, where individuals may overstate or understate their experiences with food insecurity.
3. **Lack of Longitudinal Data:** The survey captures data at a single point in time, preventing the tracking of changes in food insecurity over months or years. This limits insights into long-term trends and evolving challenges.

Suggestions :

Enhancing Awareness and Outreach – Government and community organizations should implement targeted awareness campaigns to educate people about food insecurity and available assistance programs. This should be mainly focused in rural and semi-urban areas where awareness of food insecurity is low.

Strengthening Food Assistance Programs – Expanding and improving food distribution schemes with better accessibility, transparency, and efficiency can increase participation and

awareness on the topic of food insecurity. Simplifying eligibility criteria and using Digital platforms for outreach can give better room for opportunities to reach more beneficiaries.

Improving Food Affordability and Quality – Policies should focus on price regulation for essential nutritious foods, stricter quality control in local markets, and subsidized meal programs to ensure low-income groups have access to affordable, high-quality food.

Encouraging Sustainable Food Practices – Promoting community farming, food waste reduction initiatives, and meal preparation training can provide better ideas to manage food security in an effective manner. Government support for local food markets and self-sufficiency programs will help to create more awareness and add beneficial factors to the whole topic of food insecurity.

Conclusion

Food insecurity remains a major challenge globally, which has over time impacted many vulnerable populations, in developed as well as developing countries across the globe. This study highlights the economic, social, and environmental factors leading to food insecurity, showcasing how poverty, rising food costs, and limited awareness of food assistance programs expand the issue. The research findings reveal imbalance in awareness between urban and semi-urban populations, with economic instability being the main reason for food insecurity. moreover, poor food quality, high prices, and limited access to food further restrict people from obtaining healthy nutritious meals, leading to many health problems.

To address these challenges, certain policy interventions are required. Strengthening food assistance programs, improving the affordability and quality, and promoting sustainable food practices can majorly enhance food security. Community driven initiatives, with government reforms, can bridge the gaps in the awareness and accessibility, ensuring proper food distribution. While this study gives valuable insights, more research in the future must focus on larger and more diverse data, including long term data to track the trends in food insecurity. Implementing strategies, organizations and communities can work together to create a more sustainable and food secure future for everyone.

References

- Drewnowski, A. (2022). Food insecurity has economic root causes. *Nature food*, 3(8), 555-556.
- Dasgupta, S., & Robinson, E. J. (2022). Attributing changes in food insecurity to a changing climate. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 4709.

Niles, M. T., Bertmann, F., Belarmino, E. H., Wentworth, T., Biehl, E., & Neff, R. (2020). The early food insecurity impacts of COVID-19. *Nutrients*, 12(7), 2096.

Pourmotabbed, A., Moradi, S., Babaei, A., Ghavami, A., Mohammadi, H., Jalili, C., ... & Miraghajani, M. (2020). Food insecurity and mental health: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Public health nutrition*, 23(10), 1778-1790.

Ivers, L. C., & Cullen, K. A. (2011). Food insecurity: special considerations for women. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 94(6), 1740S-1744S.

McKay, F. H., Sims, A., & Van Der Pligt, P. (2023). Measuring food insecurity in India: a systematic review of the current evidence. *Current Nutrition Reports*, 12(2), 358-367.

Gundersen, C., & Kreider, B. (2009). Bounding the effects of food insecurity on children's health outcomes. *Journal of health economics*, 28(5), 971-983.

Neves Freiria, C., Arikawa, A., Van Horn, L. T., Pires Corona, L., & Wright, L. Y. (2024). Food insecurity among older adults living in low-and middle-income countries: A scoping review. *The Gerontologist*, 64(1), gnac161.

Biete, C., Biete, A., Patriota, E. S., Gonçalves, V. S., Buccini, G., & Pizato, N. (2025). Household food insecurity and symptoms of anxiety and depression during pregnancy: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Maternal & Child Nutrition*, 21(1), e13714.

O'Hara, S., & Toussaint, E. C. (2021). Food access in crisis: Food security and COVID-19. *Ecological Economics*, 180, 106859.

Selvamani, Y., Arokiasamy, P., & Chaudhary, M. (2023). Association between food insecurity and quality of life among older adults (60+) in six low and middle-income countries. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics*, 114, 105079.

Epstein, L. H., Temple, J. L., Faith, M. S., Hostler, D., & Rizwan, A. (2024). A psychobioecological model to understand the income-food insecurity-obesity relationship. *Appetite*, 196, 107275.

Dennard, E., Kristjansson, E., Tchangalova, N., Totton, S., Winham, D., & O'Connor, A. (2022). Food insecurity among African Americans in the United States: A scoping review. *Plos one*, 17(9), e0274434.

Zhang, X., Bruening, M., & Ojinnaka, C. O. (2023). Food insecurity is inversely associated with positive childhood experiences among a nationally representative sample of children aged 0–17 years in the USA. *Public Health Nutrition*, 26(11), 2355-2365.

Burnette, C. B., Hazzard, V. M., Larson, N., Hahn, S. L., Eisenberg, M. E., & Neumark-Sztainer, D. (2023). Is intuitive eating a privileged approach? Cross-sectional and longitudinal associations between food insecurity and intuitive eating. *Public health nutrition*, 26(7), 1358-1367.